

1,3-Dipolar Cycloaddition. Part-XXVI. Stereoselective synthesis of substituted pyrrolizidines by multi-component synthetic strategy

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Abstract : Solution phase multi-component synthetic strategy was utilized to synthesize trisubstituted pyrrolizidines. The key step was the ring-forming 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition of non-stabilized azomethine ylides generated *in situ* with electron-deficient dipolarophiles. Characterization of cycloadducts were done by detailed spectroscopic analysis, and finally by single crystal XRD.

Keywords : 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition, multi-component reaction, azomethine ylide, α -amino acid.

Introduction

Synthesis of 5-membered heterocycles has gained importance over the years due to their considerable biological and pharmaceutical activity¹. To synthesize fused 5-membered ring system like substituted pyrrolizidines, 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition^{2,3} of azomethine ylides to olefinic double bond is one of the best methods. In this work, we have utilized a multi-component synthetic strategy⁴ to furnish substituted pyrrolizidines. The main advantage of multi-component reactions is that the synthetic target can be generated in a single reaction vessel in high yield.

Cycloaddition reactions of *p*-chloro diethyl benzylidenemalonate with azomethine ylides derived from L-proline and aryl aldehydes has been used to selectively generate tri-substituted pyrrolizidines. For generation of azomethine ylide the decarboxylation⁵ procedure was used where an unstable oxazolidine-5-one (**4**) was formed as intermediate; after loss of CO₂ it produced nonstabilised azomethine ylide. The azomethine ylides generated *in situ*⁶ in the reaction medium reacted with the dipolarophile (Scheme 2). 1,3-Dipolar cycloadditions of azomethine ylides are expected to be favorable if the dipolarophile is electron-deficient species⁷. For this purpose diethyl benzylidenemalonate was selected as dipolarophile⁸. In the dipolarophile, two ester groups are attached to the double bond; these electron-attracting ester groups render the double bond extremely electron-deficient.

Results and discussion

L-Proline was used to generate azomethine ylides. Azomethine ylides are generated from amino acids and aryl aldehydes through the decarboxylation procedure (Scheme 1). Dry DMF solvent was used as reaction solvent and temperature of the reactions were maintained at 120 °C. Two types of ylide formation are possible in this case W-shaped and S-shaped; these are interconvertible among themselves. From our results it was established that only S-shaped ylides participated in the cycloadditions.

The reactions carried out are shown in Scheme 2. The cycloadducts were separated from the crude reaction mixture in the pure state by chromatography. The cycloadducts were characterized by different spectroscopic techniques (¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, IR, MS) and finally by single crystal-XRD study.

In the aliphatic region of ¹H NMR no sharp singlet peak appeared due to characteristic ring proton, this eliminated the possibility to the formation of regioisomeric cycloadducts **7**. Most deshielded proton of the cycloadduct **8a** appeared at δ 4.78 [H-1] as doublet (*J* 5.9 Hz), this was coupled with δ 4.57 (d, *J* 5.9 Hz) [H-2]. In between the two doublet peaks a multiplet appeared at δ 4.63 due to [H-3a] proton. From the 2D-COSY NMR spectrum it was established that H-1 coupled with H-2, and H-3a

Scheme 1. Formation of cyclic azomethine ylides, L-proline as precursor.

coupled with protons corresponding to δ 2.10 (H-4A) and 1.52 (H-4B). These were characteristic for the cycloadduct **8a**. Stereochemistry of cycloadduct **8a** was established by single crystal-XRD study. Solid state crystal structure of cycloadduct **8a** is given in Fig. 1. Characterization of other cycloadducts in this series (**8c-d**) was done as their spectroscopical data were similar to those of cycloadduct **8a**.

Solid state assembling of cycloadduct **8a** molecules is shown in Fig. 2; this was due to weak H-bonding between two units of molecules. In this assemblage two types of H-bonding are present, as shown. Crystallographic data (excluding structural factors) for the structures in this paper have been deposited at the Cambridge Crystal-

lographic Data Centre as supplementary publication nos. CCDC860073 (cycloadduct **8a**).

Experimental

General : Commercially available ethyl acetate and petroleum ether (boiling range 60–80 °C) were distilled before use. Reaction solvent DMF was distilled under reduced pressure after keeping 72 h in presence of type 3 Å molecular sieves. Column chromatography was performed on Merck silica gel (60–120 mesh, 0.120–0.250 mm). Analytical TLC was performed on 0.25 mm Merck extra hard silica gel plates with UV254 fluorescent indicator. Melting points were recorded on an electrically heated Köfler Block apparatus. All melting points are

Scheme 2. Formation of pyrrolizidine cycloadducts.

uncorrected. 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded at ambient temperature using Bruker Avance 300 spectrometer (300 MHz for 1H and 75 MHz for ^{13}C). Chemical shifts are reported in δ , ppm with tetramethylsilane as internal reference, and coupling constants in Hz. Infrared spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer spectrum 100 FT-IR spectrometer in KBr pellets. EI-MS analysis was performed with a Perkin-Elmer Clarus 600GC-

MS instrument at 70 eV using column Elite 5 MS (30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 μ m) columns with maximum temperature 300 $^{\circ}C$. Single crystal X-ray diffraction studies of the crystalline heterocyclic compound were done with X-ray Bruker Smart Apex-II diffractometer. Refinement was done by SHELXL-97 programme.

Preparation of dipolarophile (6) :

Condensation of diethyl malonate with *p*-chloro ben-

Fig. 1. Structure of cycloadduct 8a

Fig. 2. Arrangement of molecules of 8a in the crystal.

zaldehyde in presence of piperidine as base was carried out at temperature 140 °C in dry benzene as solvent⁹. Dean-Stark apparatus was used for this purpose to remove the water from the reaction mixture. The condensed product was recovered by working up with 1(*N*) HCl followed by saturated NaHCO₃ solution, and then dried overnight over anhydrous sodium sulphate (Na₂SO₄). Finally pure product was obtained by distillation under reduced pressure, 140 °C/4 mm of Hg (yield 66%).

Characterization of dipolarophile (6) :

p-Chloro diethyl benzylidinemalonate, C₁₅H₁₉ClO₄ :

light yellow dense liquid; IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 1729, 1631, 1492, 1258, 1064 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 1.27–1.35 (6H, m, -CH₂-CH₃), 4.28–4.37 (4H, m, O-CH₂-), 7.32–7.47 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.67 (1H, s, C=CH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 13.69, 13.91, 61.52, 61.58, 126.72, 128.88, 130.48, 130.82, 131.22, 136.36, 140.35, 163.66 (C=O), 166.14 (C=O).

General procedure of cycloaddition reactions :

A solution of *p*-chloro diethyl benzylidinemalonate (2 mmol), L-proline (2 mmol) and aryl aldehyde (2 mmol) in 10 ml dry DMF solvent was taken in a 50 ml round-bottomed flask and heated at 120 °C. Progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and ¹H NMR. At the end of the reaction, the high boiling solvent DMF was removed by dilution with excess chloroform and then washing with cold water. The chloroform was removed under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator and the product was separated by column chromatography on silica gel (60–120 mesh, 0.120–0.250 mm) using different percentages of ethyl acetate in petroleum ether (60–80 °C) as eluents.

Characterisation data of cycloadducts (8a-d) :

Compound 8a :

3,3-Dicarbethoxy-1-(2-methoxyphenyl)-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-pyrrolizidine, C₂₆H₃₀ClNO₅; colourless crystals (10% ethyl acetate-hexane); reaction time : 40 min; yield : 75%; m.p. : 64–66 °C; isolated from 3% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether eluates. IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 2963, 1729, 1618, 1268, 1213, 1232, 822, 765 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 4.78 (1H, d, *J* 5.9 Hz, H-1), 4.57 (1H, d, *J* 5.9 Hz, H-2), 4.63 (1H, m, H-3a), 3.05 and 2.35 (1H, m, each, ring-CH₂-6), 1.80–2.10 (3H, m, ring-CH₂-4, 5), 1.52 (1H, m, ring-CH₂-5), 3.50 and 3.70 (1H, m each, -O-CH₂CH₃), 4.04–4.28 (2H, m, -O-CH₂-CH₃), 1.23 (3H, t, *J* 6.6 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 0.78 (3H, t, *J* 6.9 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.58 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz, H-3/A), 6.85–7.10 (5H, m, H-5/A, Ar-H/B), 7.29 (1H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz, H-6/A), 7.63 (1H, br t, *J* ~7.4 Hz, H-4/A); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 13.50, 14.15, 28.15, 29.54, 53.35, 55.03, 57.53, 60.88, 61.38, 66.62, 68.03, 68.58, 109.15, 119.73, 127.10, 127.13, 128.33, 128.66, 131.40, 131.96, 136.54, 156.53, 169.01 (C=O), 171.20 (C=O); EI-MS *m/z* 471 (M⁺), 473 (M⁺+2); Found : C, 66.32; H, 6.28; N, 2.72. C₂₆H₃₀ClNO₅ requires : C,

66.16; H, 6.41; N, 2.97. Crystal data for **8a**. $C_{26}H_{30}ClNO_5$, orthorhombic, space group $P2(1)2(1)2(1)$; $a = 10.343(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.805(4) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 20.512(7) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$, $V = 2504.4(15) \text{ \AA}^3$, $Z = 4$, $R = 0.0474$.

Compound 8b :

3,3-Dicarbethoxy-1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-pyrrolizidine, $C_{26}H_{30}ClNO_5$: colourless solid, reaction time : 30 min; yield : 72%; m.p. : 124–126 °C; isolated from 3% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether eluates. IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 2977, 1731, 1610, 1507, 1254, 1203, 1223, 830, 761 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 4.66 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, H-1), 4.32 (1H, d, J 6.0 Hz, H-2), 4.72 (1H, m, H-3a), 3.10 and 2.40 (1H, m of each, ring- CH_2 -6), 1.80–2.15 (3H, m, ring- CH_2 -4, 5), 1.55 (1H, m, ring- CH_2 -5), 3.60 and 3.78 (1H, m each, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 4.18–4.35 (2H, m, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.25 (3H, t, J 7.3 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 0.83 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 3.68 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.61 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3,5/A), 6.99–7.07 (6H, m, H-2,6/A, Ar-H/B); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 13.46, 14.11, 28.26, 29.59, 53.35, 55.03, 60.57, 61.01, 61.51, 66.47, 68.30, 72.81, 113.04, 127.38, 128.49, 131.72, 132.24, 135.98, 158.0, 168.85 (C=O), 171.07 (C=O); EI-MS m/z 471 (M^+), 473 ($\text{M}^+ + 2$); Found : C, 66.69; H, 6.22; N, 2.65; $C_{26}H_{30}ClNO_5$: requires : C, 66.16; H, 6.41; N, 2.97.

Compound 8c :

3,3-Dicarbethoxy-1,2-di-(4-chlorophenyl)-pyrrolizidine, $C_{25}H_{27}Cl_2NO_4$; reaction time : 50 min; yield : 65%; m.p. : 136–138 °C; isolated from 10% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether eluates. IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 2978, 1732, 1486, 1366, 1258, 1203, 1098, 1014, 823, 760 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 4.70 (1H, d, J 5.9 Hz, H-1), 4.24 (1H, d, J 5.9 Hz, H-2), 4.73 (1H, m, H-3a), 3.08 and 2.40 (1H, m each, ring- CH_2 -6), 1.98–2.10 (3H, m, ring- CH_2 -4, 5), 1.52 (1H, m, ring- CH_2 -5), 3.62 and 3.82 (1H, m each, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.08–4.36 (2H, m, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3$), 1.30 (3H, t, J 6.6 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 0.84 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 7.02–7.30 (8H, Ar-H); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 13.46, 14.10, 20.94, 28.31, 29.56, 53.47, 60.45, 60.99, 61.49, 66.46, 68.30, 73.09, 127.38, 127.79, 128.34, 128.78, 131.75, 132.20, 135.68, 135.90, 168.80 (C=O), 171.05 (C=O); EI-MS m/z 475 (M^+), 477 ($\text{M}^+ + 2$), 479 ($\text{M}^+ + 4$); Found : C, 63.25; H, 6.01; N,

2.85; $C_{25}H_{27}Cl_2NO_4$ requires : C, 63.03; H, 5.71; N, 2.94.

Compound 8d :

3,3-Dicarbethoxy-1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-(4-chlorophenyl)-pyrrolizidine, $C_{26}H_{30}ClNO_4$; reaction time : 40 min; yield : 62%; m.p. : 118–120 °C; isolated from 5% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether eluates. IR (KBr) ν_{\max} : 2978, 1732, 1486, 1366, 1258, 1203, 1098, 1014, 823, 760 cm^{-1} ; $^1\text{H NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 4.70 (1H, d, J 6.2 Hz, H-1), 4.23 (1H, d, J 6.2 Hz, H-2), 4.72 (1H, m, H-3a), 3.10 and 2.42 (1H, m each, ring- CH_2 -6), 1.95–2.10 (3H, m, ring- CH_2 -4, 5), 1.55 (1H, m, ring- CH_2 -5), 3.60 and 3.78 (1H, m each, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 4.12–4.34 (2H, m, $-\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 1.29 (3H, t, J 6.9 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 0.83 (3H, t, J 7.3 Hz, OCH_2CH_3), 2.18 (3H, s, $-\text{CH}_3$), 6.87 (2H, d, J 7.9 Hz, H-3,5/A), 6.97–7.16 (6H, m, H-2,6/A, Ar-H/B); $^{13}\text{C NMR}$ (CDCl_3) : δ 13.46, 14.10, 20.94, 28.31, 29.56, 53.47, 60.45, 60.99, 61.49, 66.46, 68.30, 73.09, 127.38, 127.79, 128.34, 128.78, 131.75, 132.20, 135.68, 135.90, 168.80 (C=O), 171.05 (C=O); EI-MS m/z 455 (M^+), 457 ($\text{M}^+ + 2$); Found : C, 67.98; H, 6.33; N, 3.09; $C_{26}H_{30}ClNO_4$ requires : C, 68.49; H, 6.63; N, 3.07.

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